

Variation of Fundamental Constants

The evolution of Zybertspheres which met all four Tests was so prevalent that a change in the two Fundamental Constants used - Neutron Mass N and the Gravitational Constant G - was tested. Table 1 shows how Zybertsphere parameters are affected by different N and G values, expressed as a change ratio, suggesting that gravity dynamics seems to favour Zybertspheres of similar configuration.

Table 1. Effect of changing values of Fundamental Constants, N & G, in ZC simulations at $Z=7E4$.

	Z_T	$Z_{M.core}$	$Z_{R.core}$	$Z_{V.core}$	$Z_{R.N2}$	$Z_{V.N2}$	$Z_{A.N2}$	Z_Z	$Z_{\dot{Z}}$	$Z_{A'}$	Z_p
$N=N/2$	1	0.5	0.7937	0.7937	0.7937	0.7937	0.7937	1	1	1	1
$N=N*2$	1	2	1.2599	1.2599	1.2599	1.2599	1.2599	1	1	1	1
$G=G/2$	1	1	1	1	0.7937	0.7937	0.7937	1	1	1	2
$G=G*2$	1	1	1	1	1.2599	1.2599	1.2599	1	1	1	0.5